

A Secure Framework For Controller Pilot Data Link Communications in Aviation Network

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Abstract—Controller Pilot Data Link Communications (CPDLC) enhances air traffic communication by replacing traditional voice transmissions with digital messages over Very High Frequency (VHF) radio systems. This transition improves communication resilience by providing clear, text-based instructions that reduce misunderstandings and increase bandwidth efficiency by enabling more data to be transmitted simultaneously. It benefits congested airspace by reducing radio frequency congestion and minimizing communication errors. However, due to the plain-text nature of its messages, CPDLC faces significant security challenges, making it vulnerable to cyber-attacks such as eavesdropping, modification, injection, and man-in-the-middle (MITM) attacks. This vulnerability allows motivated attackers to intercept CPDLC messages using inexpensive devices like Software-Defined Radio (SDR), HACKRF-one, and an antenna. Such breaches can lead to fatal safety incidents, severely impacting passengers and the aviation industry. To address this, we proposed a robust security framework for securing CPDLC communication by implementing critical measures, including mutual authentication, secure key establishment, and handover. The proposed framework has been tested on hardware to verify its effectiveness in practical scenarios, ensuring it aligns with existing CPDLC standards and integrates seamlessly into current systems without impacting operational efficiency. Our findings indicate that the proposed security framework enhances CPDLC's defenses against potential cyber threats while maintaining system performance, making it feasible to protect global air traffic communications.

Index Terms—Aviation, CPDLC, Handover, Security, VHF

I. INTRODUCTION

The aviation industry is seeing a significant recovery after COVID-19, and predictions suggest that by 2024, the number of flights will not only exceed those in 2019 but could double by 2030 [1]. This growth puts immense pressure on traditional air traffic control (ATC) communication systems, crucial for safe and efficient air traffic management (ATM). In 2021, ATCs managed over 19 million flights worldwide [2], relying heavily on voice communication channels.

ATCs traditionally use voice radio communications in the VHF band to coordinate flights and respond to emergencies. However, this system faces significant challenges, including delays in signal transmission due to its half-duplex nature, interference from overlapping channels, and bottlenecks at

ATC centers. These issues can lead to slower response times and operational inefficiencies and may contribute to aviation incidents [3]. For example, Boeing noted that in congested airspace, pilots often experience 20 to 45-minute delays in using voice channels for position reporting [4] disrupting ATM. Furthermore, radio frequency channel disruptions can make aircraft operate at less efficient altitudes and speeds, potentially increasing the risk of aviation accidents [5].

Therefore, to address the limitations of traditional voice communication systems in aviation, the industry is actively modernizing ATM systems through initiatives such as the United States' Next Generation National Airspace System (NextGen) [6] and Europe's Single European Sky ATM Research (SESAR) program [7]. These initiatives are designed to enhance global airspace's operational capabilities, efficiency, safety, and resilience by integrating advanced technologies. A key technology in this modernization is the CPDLC, which significantly reduces reliance on voice communications by enabling the exchange of text-based messages between pilots and ATCs. This system allows ATC to efficiently communicate flight plan updates, altitude and speed changes, and radio frequency assignments to pilots. Pilots can then respond to these messages, request new clearances, or report their statuses. CPDLC is particularly crucial in airspaces where datalink capabilities are mandatory, supporting strategic and non-emergency communications.

In Europe, CPDLC operates through the Aeronautical Telecommunications Network (ATN) using VHF Data Link Mode 2 (VDLM2), facilitating a data transmission rate of 31.5 kilobits per second [8]. Meanwhile, in the USA and Australia, it is implemented via the satellite-based Future Air Navigation System (FANS-1/A). These implementations have collectively saved over 2.28 million minutes of radio communication time [9], minimizing the need for voice communications and enabling tighter aircraft separation, enhancing airspace capacity and safety. The ongoing efforts to align the standards of ATN and FANS-1/A worldwide highlight the critical importance of CPDLC in modernizing global airspace management and advancing aviation technology.

While CPDLC offers significant benefits for aviation communication, it also introduces severe cyber security vulnera-

bilities due to the plaintext nature of messages sent over unsecured channels. With equipment such as SDR dongle, a VHF airband antenna, and an amplifier, an attacker can eavesdrop, intercept, and modify CPDLC messages. Additionally, attackers can inject false messages and impersonate controllers or pilots, gaining unauthorized control. These cyber-attacks pose severe risks to the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of communication services, potentially leading to catastrophic outcomes for the entire aviation infrastructure [10].

The European Air Traffic Management-Computer Emergency Response Team (EATM-CERT) reported numerous critical cyber-attacks on airlines in 2020. One significant incident involved hackers gaining control of LOT airline's ground control systems, resulting in operational immobility for several hours. This disruption led to the cancellation of 10 flights and significant delays for over a dozen additional flights [11]. These incidents highlight the critical cybersecurity vulnerabilities faced by airlines, which are essential for transporting diplomats, politicians, VIPs, and the general public and integral to the food supply chain.

These vulnerabilities not only threaten the safety and efficiency of air travel but also compromise the anonymity and security of sensitive individuals and cargo. Consequently, the current cybersecurity limitations in CPDLC pose significant threats with far-reaching implications. Therefore, there is an urgent need for a bandwidth-efficient, cost-effective, reliable, and resilient solution to ensure robust security and privacy for ground-air communication, effectively protecting against cyber-attacks.

A. Our Contributions

Motivated by the need to improve CPDLC system security, we propose a comprehensive mutual authentication and secure key agreement solution complemented by a robust handover process. The main contributions of this paper are as follows:

- We proposed a mutual authentication and secured key agreement solution tailored for the CPDLC system to enhance security while minimizing communication and computational costs. Our security framework employs Physical Unclonable Functions (PUF) for mutual authentication between the aircraft and ATSU and the Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) protocol to facilitate the generation of a robust and secure session key.
- Our proposed security framework is also tailored for session handover when an aircraft switches between ATSUs. It ensures secure authentication of both the aircraft and the approaching ATSU, followed by generating a session key for secure communication. Additionally, our solution supports and secures session handovers when an aircraft transitions between ATSUs that do not support CPDLC, effectively addressing this unique challenge.
- Finally, we evaluated our proposed security framework's computational and communication costs using a testbed equipped with a Raspberry PI 3B+ and processing units. The evaluation focuses on practical applicability, assessing the solution in terms of computation time, efficiency,

and payload compatibility. Our findings demonstrate that the proposed framework is effective and efficient for real-world deployment.

B. Paper Organization

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides an in-depth literature review, clearly defines the problem statement, and elaborates on the research motivation. Section 3 presents the preliminaries, offering an overview of the CPDLC operational flow, the adversary model, security objectives, and essential background information on PUFs and ECC. Section 4 details the proposed methods for mutual authentication, key exchange, and secure handover. Section 5 describes the experimental setup used to validate the proposed framework and analyzes its performance. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper by summarizing the key findings and suggesting potential avenues for future research.

II. RELATED WORK

The analysis of cybersecurity vulnerabilities in the CPDLC system has evolved through several significant studies. Initially, Strohmeier et al. [12] identified a range of threats to air-ground communication systems, including jamming, eavesdropping, message injection, and deletion. While comprehensive, their research did not cover a broader spectrum of security risks, nor did it address securing handovers between ATSUs. Building on this, Eskilsson et al. [10] demonstrated the CPDLC's vulnerability to cyber-attacks by intercepting messages using a HackRF One RTL-SDR dongle, further emphasizing the need for robust security measures to protect these communications. Subsequently, Gurtov et al. [13] highlighted the cybersecurity vulnerabilities within the CPDLC framework more deeply. They identified critical security gaps and proposed a detailed threat model. To counteract these vulnerabilities, they recommended implementing ECC, the host-identity protocol (HIP), and identity-defined networking (IDN). However, while these advanced solutions show promise, their effectiveness in real-world scenarios remains untested. Additionally, their study did not address the security challenges during the handover process between ATSUs.

Similarly, Smailes et al. [14] identified vulnerabilities in the CPDLC system to MITM attacks, especially during session handovers. They suggested a solution using Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) to enhance security without modifying existing CPDLC protocols. However, these recommendations have yet to be tested, creating uncertainty about their effectiveness and the potential impact on communication efficiency. Building upon the groundwork laid by the aforementioned studies, Griner et al. [15] have proposed an approach to enhance CPDLC's security using cryptographic methods. They suggest using a two-step authentication process based on ECC, which is theoretically sound. However, this approach faces practical challenges related to computational efficiency and communication delays. To counteract cyber attacks in CPDLC systems, Khan et al. [16] proposed a secure solution for air-to-ground communication using ECC and digital certificates.

While effective, their solution incurs a slightly higher cost compared to our proposed framework.

The existing security measures proposed for CPDLC have been designed with a narrow focus on potential threats and do not provide security for all types of handover. As a result, the existing proposed solutions have several critical shortcomings. These include (1) incompatibility with the structure of CPDLC messages and next data authority notification, (2) unpredictable performance due to the lack of implementation, and (3) high computational and time delays.

A. Problem statement and research motivation

The CPDLC system facilitates the wireless transmission of unencrypted data link messages between aircraft and ATSU. However, it is vulnerable to cyber threats due to its unsecured wireless medium and lack of robust security measures. Attackers can exploit this vulnerability using equipment such as SDR dongles, VHF airband antennas, and amplifiers to intercept and manipulate communications. As a result, attackers can impersonate legitimate ground stations or aircraft, sending false messages that could cause aircraft to deviate from planned routes or relay incorrect information to ATC. The risks are especially high during the handover phase when control transitions between different ATSUs. During this critical period, attackers can perform jamming attacks to disrupt communication services, affecting both aircraft and ground stations. This disruption sets the stage for subsequent attacks, such as MITM operations, where adversaries can intercept and alter communications, compromising message integrity, confidentiality, and authentication. Additionally, these vulnerabilities allow attackers to conduct masquerading attacks, wherein they gain unauthorized access to classified information and take control of sensitive systems. They can also eavesdrop on data traffic without the consent of the communicating parties, severely breaching the confidentiality of communications.

The combined impact of these threats highlights the urgent need for enhanced security solutions within the CPDLC system to protect against these diverse and potentially catastrophic cyber risks. For instance, a cyber incident involved a hacker group allegedly compromising ground-control computers of the state-owned Polish airline LOT, which prevented the issuance of flight plans and affected 1,400 passengers [17]. To avoid similar cyber abuses in the future, ATN must possess a high level of security and privacy. Researchers need to theoretically and experimentally address the following questions to ensure the development of a reliable and secure ground-air communication framework for the CPDLC:

- 1) How can aircraft and ATSUs ensure they are communicating with legitimate ATSUs or aircraft under adversarial conditions?
- 2) How can trust between an approaching ATSU and an aircraft be established during the handover phase?

III. PRELIMINARIES AND BACKGROUND

This section explores the operational flow of the CPDLC system, outlines the adversary model, discusses security objec-

tives for CPDLC, and discusses essential preliminary concepts for PUF and ECC.

A. Operational Flow of CPLDC

Like other stream-oriented communication systems, entities in CPDLC must establish a connection before data transfer. However, CPDLC includes a unique handover phase after data exchange, where the aircraft disconnects from ATSU₁ and initiates communication with ATSU₂. Fig. 1 depicts this process, focusing on the ground-to-ground (G-G) handover.

G-G handovers occur in situations where notification to the next authority is not required. This issue often arises when an aircraft transitions between ATSUs that do not both support CPDLC. To address this, the ICAO GOLD document [18] provides guidelines to ensure that the aircraft logs onto the new unit upon entering CPDLC-capable airspace. Following these guidelines ensures continuous data link communication, reducing the risk of miscommunication and enhancing flight safety, even without prior notification between ATSUs.

Figure 1. Message exchange before and after CPDLC handover.

Connection Establishment: CPDLC begins its process with the aircraft sending a Logon Request that includes information on supported data link applications, the aircraft's identifier, and any additional details required for flight plan correlation. The ATSU₁ then responds with a Logon Confirmation as a Logon Response, affirming the successful correlation of the aircraft's details with its flight plan. The ATSU₁ issues a CPDLC Connection Request to formally establish the data link communication channel. The aircraft completes the process by sending back a Connection Confirm message, signaling the successful establishment of the CPDLC connection for direct data communications between the aircraft and the ATSU₁.

Data Transfer: During this phase, CPDLC facilitates the exchange of commands, information, and responses between the aircraft and ATSU. The ATSU primarily issues command to the aircraft, which typically acknowledges responses like “Wilco” (will comply) or “Unable” to indicate compliance or inability to comply. This stage allows for a two-way communication flow, which is essential for the system’s operational efficiency.

Connection Handover: This critical phase ensures the seamless transition of communication from one ground station to another. In a G-G handover, ATSU₁ informs the aircraft about the upcoming authority ATSU₂ and transfers the aircraft’s logon information to ATSU₂. Following this, ATSU₂ initiates a new connection request to the aircraft, which, upon confirmation, establishes a new link for data transfer between ATSU₂ and the aircraft.

Connection Termination: The final phase occurs after a successful handover, where ATSU₁ issues a connection termination request to the aircraft. Upon receiving this request, the aircraft disconnects from ATSU₁ and continues communication with ATSU₂ until the next handover phase.

B. Adversary Model

We have adopted the Dolev-Yao adversarial model for analyzing security threats in the CPDLC system. This model demonstrates that attackers can intercept, read, modify, and manipulate wireless data transmissions between aircraft and ATSU. Consider a scenario of CPDLC handover, as depicted in Fig. 2, where the next authority is not notified. In this situation, a cyber attacker, identified as ATSU_X, targets the communication process. The attack begins with ATSU_X intercepting communications between an aircraft and ATSU₁ and ATSU₂. By analyzing these intercepted messages, ATSU_X acquires ATSU₁’s credentials. Using these credentials, ATSU_X effectively impersonates ATSU₁, sending falsified messages to the aircraft. Next, ATSU_X intercepts a connection request from ATSU₂ intended for the aircraft. Spoofing the aircraft, ATSU_X approves this request back to ATSU₂, making ATSU₂ believe it is communicating with the legitimate aircraft. ATSU_X then spoofs ATSU₂ to initiate the connection process with the actual aircraft. The aircraft is deceived into thinking it is establishing a connection with the legitimate ATSU₂. These impersonations are so seamless that neither the aircraft nor ATSU₂ detects the ongoing MITM attack. This specific handover scenario, where the next authority remains uninformed, highlights a critical vulnerability. Such vulnerabilities can compromise the safety and reliability of air traffic communications, potentially endangering lives and disrupting operations.

C. Security Goals

To ensure the CPDLC system is both secure and reliable, it must fulfill the following several critical security objectives and requirements:

Mutual Authentication and Key Agreement: This security objective is essential to ensure that both the aircraft and ATSU authenticate each other’s identities and establish a secure

Figure 2. Cyber security threats in the CPDLC system [14].

communication channel by agreeing on a session key before sending and receiving messages. This is a critical measure to prevent masqueraders from sending fake or malicious messages, which could endanger the aircraft and ATSU. It also ensures that messages come from legitimate sources, i.e., ATSU or aircraft. Typically, authentication involves using digital signatures or MAC, while key agreement utilizes protocols such as Diffie-Hellman to enable secure communication.

Integrity: In CPDLC, it is crucial to maintain the integrity of messages to ensure that they have not been tampered with during transmission. This is particularly important for messages containing critical information such as flight plans, altitude assignments, and route modifications, as any unauthorized interference could lead to critical errors, including incorrect landing procedures that could risk operational safety. To ensure that messages are genuine, unaltered, and trustworthy, it is essential to apply secure hash algorithms and MACs. These measures play a significant role in verifying the authenticity of message contents, making them reliable and accessible from any unauthorized changes.

Confidentiality: Ensuring confidentiality in the messages exchanged between aircraft and ATSU is critical to prevent unauthorized entities from accessing sensitive information. Attackers can eavesdrop on messages and obtain details such as lateral deviations, level assignments, speed assignments, and vectoring, which could lead to potential security risks. To protect the information and achieve confidentiality, the system must use encryption and session keys.

By addressing mutual authentication and key agreement,

integrity, and confidentiality, the CPDLC system can provide a secure and efficient means of communication critical to aviation operations' safety and reliability.

D. Background on PUF and ECC for Security Frameworks

In this subsection, we discuss the preliminary requirements for our proposed solution. We extensively used two crucial components: PUFs and the ECC protocol.

1) **Physical Unclonable Function:** A PUF is essential in cryptography for ensuring secure communications [19]. Our system uses PUFs for their unique ability to transform given challenges (C) into corresponding responses (R), represented as $R = \text{PUF}(C)$. Each PUF within the circuit has a unique challenge-response pair based on the system's physical structure. This uniqueness makes PUF outputs unpredictable and difficult to duplicate, providing strong authenticity to the system. The complexity of creating PUFs and their resistance to cloning or manipulation make them ideal for securing communications in the CPDLC system. Any modifications to the system directly affect the PUF outputs, making them nearly impossible to replicate. This significantly enhances security against malicious activities [20].

2) **Elliptic Curve Cryptography:** For the public key-based operations, we rely on the ECC [21], offering more lightweight solutions than the classical RSA. ECC is based on the algebraic structure of elliptic curves (ECs) over finite fields. We denote the curve in the finite field F_p with p a large prime by $E_{p(a,b)}$, defined by the equation $y^2 = x^3 + ax + b$ with a and b two constants in F_p and $\Delta = 4a^3 + 27b^2 \neq 0$. The base point generator of $E_{p(a,b)}$ of prime order q is denoted by P . The EC multiplication $R = rP = (R_x, R_y)$ with $r \in F_q$ and $R_x, R_y \in F_p$ results in a point of the EC. The security of ECC is based on two computationally hard problems.

- The Elliptic Curve Discrete Logarithm Problem, this problem states that given two EC points R and Q of $E_{p(a,b)}$, it is computationally hard for any polynomial-time bounded algorithm to determine a parameter $x \in F_q^*$, such that $Q = xR$.
- The Elliptic Curve Diffie-Hellman Problem, given two EC points $R = xP, Q = yP$ with two unknown parameters $x, y \in F_q^*$, it is computationally hard for any polynomial-time bounded algorithm to determine the EC point xyP .

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

In this section, we present a comprehensive design of the proposed security framework, which is divided into four main subsections: assumptions, registration phase, mutual authentication, and session handover. To facilitate a clear understanding of how the framework operates, we have provided detailed definitions of the symbols and terms used in Table I, which serves as a reference for the terminology used throughout the following subsections.

A. Assumptions

In CPDLC, it is assumed that ATSU's communicate with one another via secure channels [22] [23] established using a shared secret key (SK_{ATSU}). This key is a crucial element known only to the respective group of ATNs or ATSU's. The SK_{ATSU} is the foundation for secure exchanges, allowing ATSU's to securely share essential setup information, including cryptographic parameters and authenticity-related data. The SK_{ATSU} is established through a Multi-Party Key Exchange (MPKE) approach within the ATN infrastructure [23]. This method ensures that ATSU's can securely agree on a SK_{ATSU} , protecting against eavesdropping and other security threats by ensuring that all information shared among ATSU's remains secure.

B. Registration phase

The CPDLC system's initialization phase involves a comprehensive offline registration process before the equipment becomes operational. This step is carried out in a secure, physically isolated facility with controlled access, effectively preventing electronic eavesdropping threats and TEMPEST interference. The registration data is manually entered into the system using secure, offline computers not connected to any network. Physical documents and media are used to transfer data between devices when necessary. The authenticity and integrity of all components and data are verified through unique serial numbers, barcodes, or QR codes, with multiple personnel involved to ensure accuracy and security. All registration data is stored in secure, tamper-evident physical storage to prevent unauthorized access. Detailed logs of the registration process are maintained, and regular audits are conducted to verify the integrity of the registration data and equipment. Only rigorously screened and verified personnel are allowed to participate in this process, ensuring a high level of security that effectively protects against cyber-attacks. These strict security measures ensure the integrity and security of the entire setup. The complete registration process is illustrated in Fig. 3 and explained as follows:

Figure 3. Aircraft Registration With ATSU.

Table I
NOTATION AND DESCRIPTION

Notation	Description	Notation	Description
International Civil Aviation Organization Address	$ICAO_A$	Temporary (pseudo) identity of AS	τ_{AS}
Public and private element of AS and ATSU	$(Y, X, R), (y, x, r)$	Message, where i_{th} is the message number	M_i
Operator: Equality, Not Equal	$\equiv?, \neq$	Concatenation, Scalar Multiplication	$\ , \cdot$
Truncated to first 24 bits	T_{24}	H, Bit-wise XOR	H, \oplus
Message Authentication Code	$H_\theta, H_\beta, H_{SK}, H_{SK'}$	If true then continue else abort	$T - C/E - A$
Authentication Successful, Connection Termination	AS, CT	Nonces	N_1, N_2, N_3, N_4
Challenge, Response, Embedded PUF	C_{AS}, R_{AS}, P_{AS}	Fetch From Memory	$Fetch_M$
MAKE	Mutual Authentication & Key Exchange		

- 1) **Step 1:** The $ATSU_1$ begins the process by creating a unique challenge, denoted as C_{AS} , and prepares a message M_1 containing $ATSU_1$ identity ID_{ATSU_1} and C_{AS} . This message M_1 is then sent to the aircraft (AS).
- 2) **Step 2:** Upon receiving message M_1 , the AS uses its onboard PUF hardware P_{AS} to generate the unique response $R_{AS} = P_{AS}(C_{AS})$. It then hashes this response to produce the digest $\theta = H(R_{AS})$. The AS then creates its temporary identity τ_{AS} by hashing the concatenation of its ICAO code $ICAO_{AS}$ and R_{AS} and truncates this hash to the first 24 bits. Following this, it sends a new message M_2 which includes $ICAO_{AS}$, τ_{AS} , and R_{AS} , to $ATSU_1$. Lastly, AS also stores ID_{ATSU_1} , θ , and τ_{AS} for future communications.
- 3) **Step 3:** Upon receiving the message M_2 , the $ATSU_1$ securely stores $ICAO_{AS}$, τ_{AS} , R_{AS} , and C_{AS} , thereby completing the secure registration process.

C. Mutual Authentication:

In this subsection, we discuss the mutual authentication process of the proposed framework. To achieve mutual authentication, four messages are exchanged, shown in Fig. 4.

- **Step 1:** The process begins with the AS retrieving τ_{AS} from its memory. The AS then selects a secret random value y and computes its public element Y by multiplying y with a base point P on an elliptic curve. Following this, the AS generates a nonce N_1 and uses it, along with τ_{AS} , ID_{ATSU_1} , and Y to compute a MAC, labeled MAC_1 . This MAC is designed to authenticate the AS to the $ATSU_1$. Finally, the AS incorporates τ_{AS} , ID_{ATSU_1} , Y , N_1 , and MAC_1 into a logon request message M_1 which is then sent to $ATSU_1$.
- **Step 2:** Upon receiving the logon request message M_1 , $ATSU_1$ first checks the freshness of nonce N_1 to protect against replay attacks. If N_1 is old, the connection is terminated to ensure security. Once N_1 is confirmed fresh, $ATSU_1$ searches for τ_{AS} and retrieves the corresponding challenge C_{AS} and response R_{AS} from its memory. Using R_{AS} , $ATSU_1$ computes the digest β , crucial for the AS authentication. This digest is used to compute MAC'_1 , computed using received τ_{AS} , ID_{ATSU_1} , Y and N_1 which is then compared with the received MAC_1 . A

match between $MAC'_1 \equiv? MAC_1$ confirms that the message originated from a legitimate AS and ensures it has not been altered during transmission, thus ensuring the authenticity and integrity of the message. To authenticate itself back to the AS, $ATSU_1$ generates a new nonce, N_2 , selects a random value x , and computes its public component, $X = xP$. It then computes $MAC_2 = H_\beta(N_2||X)$ and sends logon response message M_2 , containing N_2 , X , and MAC_2 back to the AS for further processing.

- **Step 3:** Upon receiving message M_2 , the AS checks nonce N_2 to ensure message freshness and prevent replay attacks. If N_2 is outdated, the connection is terminated. If validated as fresh, AS proceeds to compute a MAC, designated MAC'_2 , using the digest θ , which incorporates N_2 and X . A match between the computed MAC'_2 and the received MAC_2 ($MAC'_2 \equiv? MAC_2$) confirms $ATSU_1$ authenticity and ensures the integrity of the received message M_2 . Upon successful verification, AS stores X and prepares for the next phase by awaiting the Connection Request message from $ATSU_1$.
- **Step 4:** Simultaneously, after sending a logon response $ATSU_1$ creates a new nonce, N_3 , and uses its random secret x along with the received Y to compute the session key, $SK = H_\beta(xY||N_3)$. Using this SK , $ATSU_1$ computes a new MAC, $\varphi = H_{SK}(N_3||Payload)$, by including N_3 and the CPDLC payload data. The payload includes aircraft identification, requested service, flight information (position, altitude, heading, flight plan), message type and priority, and the requested ATC data authority. This MAC is essential for ensuring the integrity and source of the message and that both $ATSU_1$ and the AS use the same session key. After these checks, $ATSU_1$ sends the connection request message M_3 to the AS.
- **Step 5:** Upon receiving message M_3 , the AS first checks nonce N_3 for freshness. If the message is old, the connection is terminated. If the nonce is valid, AS computes its session key, $SK' = H_\theta(yX||N_3)$, using its secret value y , $ATSU_1$ public component X , and nonce N_3 . Subsequently, the AS then computes a new MAC, $\varphi' = H_{SK'}(N_3||Payload)$. If φ' matches the received φ , it confirms the successful establishment of the session key. To ensure to $ATSU_1$ that it correctly generated the

Figure 4. Proposed CPDLC security framework with Mutual authentication and Key exchange processes.

session key, AS generates a new nonce N_4 and computes another MAC, $MAC_4 = H_{SK'}(N_4 || Payload)$. The payload consists of the acceptance or rejection of the request, the reason for rejection, the assigned controller's identifier, communication instructions, and the next data link address. Subsequently, it then prepares and sends a new message, M_4 , containing N_4 and MAC_4 , back to $ATSU_1$ for further verification.

- **Step 6:** Upon receiving message M_4 , $ATSU_1$ checks nonce N_4 for freshness to prevent replays. If fresh, $ATSU_1$ computes a MAC, MAC_4' , using $H_{SK'}$ with received N_4 and payload. A match confirms the integrity of the message and secures the establishment of the session key, completing the mutual authentication and key agreement between $ATSU_1$ and the AS.

D. Session Handover Phase

In this subsection, we discuss the ground base handover for the AS where the current $ATSU_1$ will send a Logon Forwarding message to the approaching $ATSU_2$. The proposed security framework for handover is depicted in Fig. 5.

- **Step 1:** The handover process begins with $ATSU_1$ generating a nonce N_1 and a MAC, $MAC_{ATSU} = H_{\beta}(SK_{ATSU})$, using a digest applied to the pre-shared session key SK_{ATSU} for secure communication between

$ATSU_1$ and $ATSU_2$. Next, $ATSU_1$ prepares the message M_1 , which includes N_1 and an encrypted segment containing MAC_{ATSU} and ID_{ATSU_2} . This segment is encrypted using the session key SK . The purpose of M_1 is to inform the AS of the upcoming transition to $ATSU_2$. Simultaneously, $ATSU_1$ prepares a Logon Forwarding message M_2 for $ATSU_2$. This message includes β , $ICAO_{AS}$, τ_{AS} , ID_{ATSU_1} , and Y , all encrypted with SK_{ATSU} . This M_2 message is then sent to $ATSU_2$.

- **Step 2:** Upon receiving message M_1 , the AS first verifies the freshness of the message to ensure it hasn't been replayed; a replay would result in terminating the connection. If the message is confirmed as fresh, the AS decrypts it using the SK , extracting message components for future communications. These include the identity of the upcoming $ATSU_2$ and a secret component, MAC_{ATSU} . This information is critical for setting up a secure and authenticated communication with $ATSU_2$ for subsequent interactions.
- **Step 3:** Upon receiving M_2 , $ATSU_2$ verifies nonce N_2 to ensure the message is fresh and not a replay. Following this security check, $ATSU_2$ decrypts M_2 to retrieve crucial elements such as β , $ICAO_{AS}$, τ_{AS} , ID_{ATSU_1} , and Y , which are vital for subsequent steps in securing communication with the AS. To establish a session key

Figure 5. Proposed CPDLC security framework for session handover.

with AS, $ATSU_2$ generates a new nonce, N_3 , and a secret random value, r . It then computes the public element $R = rP$ and derives the session key $SK_2 = H_\beta(rY || N_3)$, which is intended to secure future communications. In order to affirm its authenticity and verify that both AS and $ATSU_2$ are synchronized with the correct session key, $ATSU_2$ computes a MAC, $MAC'_{ATSU} = H_\beta(SK_{ATSU})$. This MAC serves as a secret element to prove the integrity and authenticity of $ATSU_2$ at the AS side. Moreover, $ATSU_2$ computes another MAC using SK_2 , $\eta = H_{SK_2}(N_3 || MAC'_{ATSU} || ID_{ATSU_2} || R)$. This computation integrates N_3 , MAC'_{ATSU} , ID_{ATSU_2} , and R , ensuring the message's integrity, authenticity, and non-repudiation. Finally, $ATSU_2$ prepares the message M_3 , which includes N_3 , ID_{ATSU_2} , R , and η in the M_3 which is then sent to AS, for verification.

- **Step 4:** Upon receiving message M_3 , the AS validates the nonce N_3 , a crucial step for ensuring the message's timeliness and protecting against replay attacks. If the message is detected as old, the connection will be terminated to maintain security. If the message is confirmed as fresh, the AS proceeds to derive a session key, $SK'_2 = H_\beta(yR || N_3)$. Using this newly computed session key, the AS calculates a MAC, $\eta' = H_{SK'_2}(N_3 || MAC_{ATSU} || ID_{ATSU_2} || R)$. This computed MAC η' is then compared with the received MAC η to verify that the message originates from the legitimate $ATSU_2$, has not been altered, and both AS and $ATSU_2$ possess the same session key. To further assure $ATSU_2$ of the successful session key computation, the

AS generates a new nonce, N_4 , and computes another MAC, $MAC_5 = H_{SK'_2}(N_4 || \tau_{AS} || MAC_{ATSU})$, using the session key SK'_2 . This MAC_5 signals to $ATSU_2$ that the AS has correctly derived the session key, thereby aligning both entities on the same encryption parameters. Finally, the AS prepares and sends message M_4 , which includes N_4 and the computed MAC_5 , to $ATSU_2$, thereby completing this phase of communication.

- **Step 5:** Upon receiving the connection response, $ATSU_2$ verifies the freshness by checking nonce N_4 and computes $MAC'_5 = H_{SK'_2}(N_4 || \tau_{AS} || MAC_{ATSU})$. A match with the received MAC_5 confirms the message's authenticity and validates possession of the correct SK_2 , completing the handover process and establishing a secure session key between $ATSU_2$ and the AS. Following this, AS receives a termination request from $ATSU_1$ and closes the connection with $ATSU_1$ by sending a termination confirmation request.

V. PERFORMANCE AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

This section provides a comprehensive overview of the performance results and findings. The proposed security framework is assessed using various metrics, such as computational efficiency, storage utilization, communication costs, and security features. Table II demonstrates that the proposed security framework successfully integrates key security properties, including confidentiality, message integrity, freshness, anonymity, and mutual authentication. These features enhance the framework's resilience against various attacks, such as replay, injection, impersonation, modification and MITM. A

comparison with existing schemes [14], [16] reveals that our framework offers significant improvements, particularly in providing comprehensive protection against all major attacks and ensuring identity concealment. However, while [11] also comprehensively covers all major security aspects, it incurs higher communication and computation costs compared with our proposed security framework.

Table II
SECURITY FEATURE COMPARISON OF PROPOSED SECURITY FRAMEWORK VS. CONVENTIONAL PROTOCOLS

Security Features	[11]	[14]	[16]	Proposed Framework
Authentication	✓	✓	✓	✓
Integrity	✓	✓	✓	✓
Confidentiality	✓	×	✓	✓
Anonymity	✓	×	×	✓
Forward secrecy	✓	✓	✓	✓
Injection	✓	✓	✓	✓
Replay Attack	✓	✓	✓	✓
MITM	✓	✓	✓	✓
Masquerading attacks	✓	✓	✓	✓
Eavesdropping	✓	×	✓	✓

✓: Secure against attack / Preserve a security attribute, ×: Vulnerable/non-accomplishment of the security attribute

Experimental setup: The cryptographic primitives for our proposed framework were implemented using version 1.60 of the Bouncy Castle (BC) library on two different systems: a Raspberry PI 3B+ (R-PI) with a 64-bit quad-core 1.4GHz processor and 1GB of RAM and a Core-i7 computer (PC) with a 2.2GHz processor and 16GB of RAM. To ensure the accuracy and reliability of our performance measurements, we utilized the Java Microbenchmark Harness (JMH) toolkit, version 1.21, to assess the time required for cryptographic operations on both the R-PI+ and the PC.

Computational cost: The average processing times for critical cryptographic operations on different hardware platforms are depicted in Table III. On the Raspberry PI 3B+, Elliptic Curve (EC) Addition (A) takes $156.8 \mu s$, EC Multiplication (M) requires $32,800 \mu s$, SHA-256 hashing (H) is completed in $13.52 \mu s$, and AES encryption/decryption (AES) occurs in $53.86 \mu s$. Conversely, on a PC, EC Addition (A) is executed in $4.86 \mu s$, EC Multiplication (M) in $1148.2 \mu s$, SHA-256 hashing (H) in $1.02 \mu s$, and AES encryption/decryption (AES) in $2.90 \mu s$. These results affirm the efficiency of the proposed protocol on both hardware's.

Table III
EXECUTION TIME (IN μs) OF PROPOSED FRAMEWORK ON HARDWARE'S

Device	R-PI	PC
Library	BC	BC
A	156.8 ± 0.7	4.866 ± 0.005
M	32800 ± 20	1148.2 ± 0.8
H	13.52 ± 0.04	1.023 ± 0.002
E / D	53.86 ± 0.17	2.90 ± 0.03

Table IV comprehensively compares the computational costs between our proposed framework and conventional protocols

for registration, mutual authentication, and key agreement. Our findings highlight several significant advantages of our framework. During the registration phase, our solution requires only $H_{2T} + PUF_{1T}$, making it more efficient compared to the lack of detailed cost breakdowns in traditional protocols [11], [16]. In the mutual authentication phase, our framework incurs a total cost of $H_{1T} + R_{6T} + SM_{4T} + MAC_{10T}$, which is more streamlined than conventional methods. Notably, in the hand-over phase, our framework demonstrates superior efficiency with a total cost of $R_{5T} + SM_{3T} + MAC_{8T} + D_{2T} + E_{2T}$, compared to [11]'s $H_{6T} + M_{11T} + A_{5T} + D_{1T} + E_{1T}$ and [16]'s $H_{10T} + M_{16T} + A_{3T} + E_{3T} + D_{3T}$. These results underscore the effectiveness of our framework, showcasing its competitive computational efficiency across crucial operational phases.

Storage Cost: Our security framework utilizes 256 bits for hashing to ensure data integrity. We allocate 32 bits for nonce's to maintain session uniqueness and security. Additionally, we use 128-bit MAC tags to authenticate and verify the integrity of our communications, while each communication entity is identified using a 24-bit identifier.

Data overhead: We assign the aforementioned storage cost to every message in the proposed security framework.

Authentication data overhead: The authentication phase of the proposed security framework involves four key steps in the message exchange between $ATSU_1$ and the aircraft. Initially, the aircraft sends a Logon message M_1 to $ATSU_1$ containing its 24-bit temporary ID (τ_{AS}), 24-bit $ATSU_1$ ID (ID_{ATSU_1}), 256-bit public element Y , 32-bit nonce N_1 , and 128-bit MAC tag MAC_1 , resulting in a total of 464 bits. Following this, $ATSU_1$ sends a Logon Response M_2 , which includes a 32-bit nonce N_2 , its 256-bit public element X , and a 128-bit MAC tag MAC_2 , totaling 416 bits. The subsequent message M_3 serves as a connection request and contains the 32-bit nonce N_3 and 128-bit MAC tags ψ totaling 160 bits. The final message M_4 sent by the aircraft to $ATSU_1$ includes a 32-bit nonce N_4 and a 128-bit MAC tag MAC_4 , making up 160 bits. This sequence of messages secures each phase of communication between the aircraft and $ATSU_1$ and is depicted in Fig. 6.

Figure 6. Data overhead comparison of proposed framework during authentication and key exchange.

Table IV
COMPUTATION COST COMPARISON OF PROPOSED FRAMEWORK VS. CONVENTIONAL PROTOCOLS

A	Phase	Aircraft	ATSU ₁	ATSU ₂	Total Cost
[11]	Handover	$H_{4T}+M_{6T}+A_{3T}+E_{1T}$	$H_{2T}+M_{5T}+A_{2T}+D_{1T}$	-	$H_{6T}+M_{11T}+A_{5T}+D_{1T}+E_{1T}$
[16]	Handover	$H_{4T}+M_{6T}+A_{1T}+E_{2T}+D_{1T}$	$H_{3T}+M_{4T}+A_{1T}+E_{1T}+D_{1T}$	$H_{3T}+M_{6T}+A_{1T}+D_{1T}$	$H_{10T}+M_{16T}+A_{3T}+E_{3T}+D_{3T}$
Proposed	Registration	$H_{2T}+PUF_{1T}$	-	-	$H_{2T}+PUF_{1T}$
	Authentication	$R_{3T}+SM_{2T}+MAC_{5T}$	$H_{1T}+R_{3T}+SM_{2T}+MAC_{5T}$	-	$H_{1T}+R_{6T}+SM_{4T}+MAC_{10T}$
	Handover	$R_{1T}+SM_{1T}+MAC_{3T}+D_{1T}$	$R_{2T}+MAC_{1T}+E_{2T}$	$R_{2T}+SM_{2T}+MAC_{4T}+D_{1T}$	$R_{5T}+SM_{3T}+MAC_{8T}+D_{2T}+E_{2T}$

Note: A = Approach, H = Hash, M = EC Multiplication, A = EC Addition, E = Encryption, D = Decryption, Dash(-) = Not Required

Handover data overhead: The handover process in the proposed security framework is initiated by ATSU₁, which sends an 184-bit message M_1 to the aircraft. This message includes a 32-bit nonce N_1 and a 128-bit encrypted MAC, concatenated with the identifier of the next ATSU₂. Subsequently, ATSU₁ forwards a 488-bit logon forwarding message M_2 containing a 32-bit nonce N_2 , a 128-bit encrypted digest β the aircraft's 24-bit temporary ID (τ_{AS}), ATSU₁'s 24-bit ID, and the aircraft's 256-bit public element Y . Continuing the handover process, ATSU₂ prepares to establish a connection request by sending a 440-bit message M_3 to the aircraft. This message comprises a 32-bit nonce N_3 , ATSU₂'s 256-bit public element R , and a 128-bit MAC. In response, the aircraft sends a final 160-bit connection response message M_4 , which includes a 32-bit nonce and a 128-bit MAC. This structured sequence ensures secure and efficient communication and authentication throughout the handover process, as depicted in Fig. 7.

Figure 7. Data overhead comparison of the proposed framework during handover.

Integration of proposed framework within CPDLC The proposed security framework enhances the CPDLC system by introducing defenses against cyber threats while minimizing message sizes and optimizing system performance. This targeted approach ensures the system's robustness is improved without compromising the speed and efficiency of message transmission. During the authentication phase, to ensure proper formatting and synchronization, the message sizes and processing times after adding 232 bits for the CPDLC encoder are as follows: M_1 processes 696 bits in

0.022 seconds, M_2 handles 648 bits in 0.020 seconds, and both M_3 and M_4 manage 392 bits in 0.012 seconds each. These details are presented in Table V.

Table V
CPDLC MESSAGE SIZE (IN BITS) DURING AUTHENTICATION AFTER PROPOSED FRAMEWORK INTEGRATION

M	MS	RS FEC	AVLC Frame	8208(x.25) Header	TS	ML	TR (sec)
M_1	464					696	0.022
M_2	416	16	104	24	88	648	0.020
M_3	160	16	104	24	88	392	0.012
M_4	160					392	0.012

M: Message, MS: Message Size, RS FEC: Reed Solomon Forward Error Correction, AVLC: Aviation VHF Link Control, TS: Training Sequence, ML: Message Length, TR: Transmission Rate

Table VI
CPDLC MESSAGE SIZE (IN BITS) DURING HANDOVER AFTER PROPOSED FRAMEWORK INTEGRATION

M	MS	RS FEC	AVLC Frame	8208(x.25) Header	TS	ML	TR (sec)
M_1	184					416	0.013
M_2	488	16	104	24	88	720	0.022
M_3	440	16	104	24	88	672	0.021
M_4	160					392	0.012

M: Message, MS: Message Size, RS FEC: Reed Solomon Forward Error Correction, AVLC: Aviation VHF Link Control, TS: Training Sequence, ML: Message Length, TR: Transmission Rate

The proposed security framework for the CPDLC handover phase involves a structured exchange of four messages between ATSU_s and the aircraft, each including an additional 232 bits for CPDLC encoding to ensure proper formatting and synchronization. The initial message M_1 from ATSU₁ to the aircraft is 416 bits and transmitted in 0.013 seconds. The second message M_2 a Logon Forwarding Message from ATSU₁ to ATSU₂, is 720 bits and takes 0.022 seconds to send. The third message M_3 a connection request from ATSU₂ to the aircraft, is 672 bits and transmitted in 0.021 seconds. The fourth message M_4 a connection confirmation from the aircraft to ATSU₂, is 392 bits and takes 0.012 seconds to transmit. VDLm2 communication, operating at a data transfer rate of 31.5 Kbps, supports these rapid transmissions, ensuring efficient and timely message delivery. This high-speed

capability is crucial for meeting ICAO's requirements and enhancing CPDLC system performance. Overall, the proposed security framework meets ICAO's requirements through its structured approach to managing message sizes and optimizing transmission times, as detailed in Table VI.

VI. CONCLUSION

CPDLC is now widely adopted as a digital communication mode for ATC due to its superior resilience and bandwidth efficiency compared to traditional voice-based communication. However, CPDLC faces security challenges such as eavesdropping, spoofing, MITM attacks, message replay, and impersonation attacks, which pose risks to individuals, service providers, and the aviation industry. To address these issues, we proposed a lightweight and robust security framework that integrates AES, ECC, PUF, MAC, and message digest. Our solution ensures mutual authentication, key establishment, and handover mechanisms to secure CPDLC communications. The proposed security framework integrates seamlessly with the CPDLC system, ensuring rapid and precise communication.

The proposed security framework's performance is evident from the minimal message cost in both the authentication and handover phases, coupled with low transmission times. In the authentication phase, M_1 handles 696 bits in 0.022 seconds, M_2 processes 648 bits in 0.020 seconds, and both M_3 and M_4 manage 392 bits in 0.012 seconds each. During the handover phase, M_1 transmits 416 bits in 0.013 seconds, M_2 handles 720 bits in 0.022 seconds, M_3 manages 672 bits in 0.021 seconds, and M_4 processes 392 bits in 0.012 seconds. By leveraging VDLm2's capability of 31.5 Kbps, even the largest messages are transmitted efficiently, meeting ICAO requirements and enhancing CPDLC communications for optimal performance.

Our future work will focus on securing air-to-ground handovers for CPDLC, specifically where logon forwarding and next authority information are not sent by the previous ATSU to the approaching ATSU. This requires the aircraft to initiate the handover process. By enhancing the security of CPDLC in these scenarios, we aim to improve the reliability of air traffic communications and meet the evolving needs of modern aviation.

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REFERENCES

- [1] J. Žvinys and D. Rudinskas, "Investigation of the application of cpdpc to aerodrome air traffic control procedures," *Aviation*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 95–103, 2023.
- [2] International Air Transport Association, "Industry statistics fact sheet," 2021, accessed: March 27, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iata.org/en/iatarepository/publications/economic-reports/airline-industry-economic-performance---october-2021---data-tables/>
- [3] H. Sathaye, G. Noubir, and A. Ranganathan, "On the implications of spoofing and jamming aviation datalink applications," in *Proceedings of the 38th Annual Computer Security Applications Conference*, 2022, pp. 548–560.

- [4] Boeing, "Boeing Aero Magazine," https://www.boeing.com/commercial/aeromagazine/aero_02/textonly/fo02txt.html, accessed: July 1, 2024.
- [5] G. Dave, G. Choudhary, V. Sihag, I. You, and K.-K. R. Choo, "Cyber security challenges in aviation communication, navigation, and surveillance," *Computers & Security*, vol. 112, p. 102516, 2022.
- [6] Federal Aviation Administration, "Next generation air transportation system (NextGen)," 2022, accessed: March 27, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.faa.gov/nextgen/>
- [7] M. Wernberg, "Security and privacy of controller pilot data link communication," 2018.
- [8] S. Khan, G. S. Gaba, and A. Gurtov, "A federated learning based security for controller pilot data link communication," in *33rd Congress of the International Council of the Aeronautical Sciences, ICAS, Stockholm, Sweden, ICAS*, 2022, pp. 1–13.
- [9] I. L3Harris Technologies, "Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) data communications (data comm) user information," <https://www.l3harris.com/datacomm>, 2022, accessed: 28 June 2024.
- [10] S. Eskilsson, H. Gustafsson, S. Khan, and A. Gurtov, "Demonstrating ADS-B and CPDLC attacks with software-defined radio," in *2020 Integrated Communications Navigation and Surveillance Conference (ICNS)*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 1B2–1.
- [11] S. Khan, G. S. Gaba, A. Braeken, P. Kumar, and A. Gurtov, "AKAASH: A realizable authentication, key agreement, and secure handover approach for controller-pilot data link communications," *International Journal of Critical Infrastructure Protection*, vol. 42, p. 100619, 2023.
- [12] M. Strohmeier, "Security in next generation air traffic communication networks," Ph.D. dissertation, University of Oxford, 2016.
- [13] A. Gurtov, T. Polishchuk, and M. Wernberg, "Controller-pilot data link communication security," *Sensors*, vol. 18, no. 5, p. 1636, 2018.
- [14] J. Smalles, D. Moser, M. Smith, M. Strohmeier, V. Lenders, and I. Martinovic, "You talkin' to me? exploring practical attacks on controller pilot data link communications," in *Proceedings of the 7th ACM on Cyber-physical System Security Workshop*, 2021, pp. 53–64.
- [15] D. Getachew and J. H. Griner, "An elliptic curve based authentication protocol for controller-pilot data link communications," in *Integrated CNS Conference & Workshop*, 2005.
- [16] S. Khan, A. Gurtov, A. Breaken, and P. Kumar, "A security model for controller-pilot data communication link," in *2021 Integrated Communications Navigation and Surveillance Conference (ICNS)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–10.
- [17] "Hack attack grounds airplanes," 2022, accessed on 26.07.2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bankinfosecurity.com/hack-attack-grounds-airplanes-a-833/>
- [18] ICAO, *Global Operational Data Link Document (GOLD)*, 2nd ed., 2013, accessed: 2024-07-05. [Online]. Available: https://www.icao.int/APAC/Documents/edocs/GOLD_2Edition.pdf
- [19] S. Khan, G. S. Gaba, A. Gurtov, N. Mäurer, T. Graupl, and C. Schmitt, "Enhancing cybersecurity for LDACS: a secure and lightweight mutual authentication and key agreement protocol," in *2023 IEEE/AIAA 42nd Digital Avionics Systems Conference (DASC)*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–10.
- [20] S. Khan, G. S. Gaba, A. Gurtov, L. J. Jansen, N. Mäurer, and C. Schmitt, "Post quantum secure handover mechanism for next generation aviation communication networks," *IEEE Transactions on Green Communications and Networking*, 2024.
- [21] N. Koblitz, "Elliptic curve cryptosystems," *Mathematics of computation*, vol. 48, no. 177, pp. 203–209, 1987.
- [22] M. Olive, "Efficient datalink security in a bandwidth-limited mobile environment—an overview of the aeronautical telecommunications network (atn) security concept," in *20th DASC. 20th Digital Avionics Systems Conference (Cat. No. 01CH37219)*, vol. 2. IEEE, 2001, pp. 9E2–1.
- [23] N. Maurer, T. Graupl, C. Schmitt, C. Rihacek, and B. Haindl, "A secure ground handover protocol for Idacs," in *Proceedings of International Workshop on ATM/CNS 2022 International Workshop on ATM/CNS*. Electronic Navigation Research Institute, 2022, pp. 1–8.